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AI, Trust, and Consumers' online purchase intentions: Examining the Roles of Disinformation, Transparency, and Digital Literacy

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ABSTRACT

Over the last few years, a rapid increase in the use of artificial intelligence has been seen in the field of digital marketing, which has transformed how consumers evaluate online content and make purchase decisions. It is true that AI can greatly help the marketers in personalization of marketing messages, but this new technology also may hurt trust, which can lead to reduced purchase intentions. This study looks at how perceived AI disinformation and perceived AI transparency effect consumers' online purchase intentions by keeping the consumers' trust as mediator and treating digital literacy as moderator to see whether higher levels of literacy can have positive influence on consumer trust. Furthermore, this work has utilized the Theory of Planned Behaviour, Signaling Theory, Elaboration Likelihood Model and FAT framework. Additionally, this research uses a quantitative, cross-sectional research design and collected data from 300 online shoppers in Pakistan through convenience sampling, where constructs were adapted from prior studies and relationships will be tested through Structural Equation Modeling. Lastly, the goal of this study is to help advance theoretical understanding by integrating trust, transparency and digital literacy in AI marketing research and provide workable insights to develop effective AI-driven marketing strategies that enhance customers' confidence and increases their purchase intentions.

Key Words: AI Generated Content, Digital Marketing, Consumer Purchase Intentions, Disinformation, Transparency, Digital Literacy, Consumer Behaviour.

Introduction

AI integration in marketing have greatly changed how digital content influences the way brands communicate, engage consumers and how purchase decisions are formed. Nowadays, AI is responsible for creation, distribution and management of online content at different levels, such as, it can range from personalized recommendations to automated chat-bots (Chen, et al., 2024; Hermann & Puntoni, 2024). With AI usage the level of efficiency and personalization can significantly increase, but it may come with a cost of spread of AI generated disinformation and the lack of transparency about the role of AI in content creation (Ruiz, 2023; Labrecque, et al., 2025). These concerns are important when it comes to shapping consumer trust, which is a well-known driver of consumers' online purchase intentions (Beck, et al., 2023; Wang, et al., 2022).

There has been many studies focused on the usefulness of AI in business and marketing (Gupta, et al., 2024; Ziakis & Vlachopoulou, 2023), however, fewer studies have explored it's negative impacts. The risks of using AI are sometimes are substantial and can be seen when it comes to understanding how can AI can fabricate or create a misleading content, which may hurt consumers' trust (Sahebi & Formosa, 2025; Jobin, et al., 2019). This is because disinformation whether intentional or unintentional may lead to negative perception about the product claims or marketing message, which can negatively impact consumers' purchase intentions. Whereas, being transparent about the use of AI in marketing messages or advertisements has shown to improve the perception of credibility and also leads to increasing trust (Schmidt, et al., 2020; Zerilli, et al., 2023).

Furthermore, it has been seen that when consumers trust the online marketing content, their attitudes leads towards behavior. Many studies such as, Singh et al. (2024) and Soleimani (2021) argue that trust in online shopping platforms helps reduce consumers' perceived risk and enhances their confidence in the digital messages,

which can improve the purchase chances. This is further solidified by Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which believes that confidence built through trust can positively influence consumers' purchase intentions, because it not only influences attitudes but also their readiness to act. It is further supported by Signaling Theory (Spence, 1973), which suggests that transparency acts like a positive signal, whereas, disinformation is seen as a negative one; both of these are interpreted through trust.

While there has been a growing knowledge base focused at trust, transparency and AI related risks, fewer studies have explored that how digital literacy may influence these relationships. Studies like Tiernan, et al., (2023) and Qadri, et al., (2025) highlighted that the ability of consumers to critically evaluate online content has become increasingly important in today's time. It is further supported by studies such as, Yang et al., (2024) and Lopez & Garza, (2023) who argue that higher level of digital literacy may act like a buffer between the negative effects of AI disinformation and it can also substantially increasing the positive impact of AI transparency by helping consumers to interpret the disclosures more effectively. Whereas, not all consumers are at the same literacy level, therefore, studying moderating effect of literacy can serve as positive construct in this research.

A significant gap exists in the current body of knowledge because many of the previous studies has explored disinformation and transparency, however, little work has been done in regards to studying these by incorporating the mediating effect of trust and moderating effect of digital literacy. Furthermore, most of the research has explored developed nations and little has been seen in under-developing economies like Pakistan, where online shopping has been growing but the concerns regarding the use of AI are also increasing (Islam, et al., 2024).

Based on these, this research aims to answer that how does the perceived AI-generated disinformation and perceived AI transparency influence purchase intention, and how are these relationships mediated by consumer trust and moderated by digital literacy? By answering these questions, this study aims to contribute towards the implications and uses of AI in digital marketing and provide insights to design AI driven communication strategies, which promote transparency, build trust and help drive purchase intentions.

Literature Review

Consumers' online purchase intentions:

Consumers' online purchase intentions is defined as the customers' willingness or likelihood of making a purchase through online platforms Many researchers rely on this construct in consumer studies as it helps them study how people evaluate and react to online marketing content (Gupta, et al., 2024).

There are several limitations to studying the actual purchase behaviour including the absence of actual purchase data, privacy restrictions and scattered nature of online activity. As a result, many chose to study perceived behaviour, an approach that is also supported by the Ajzen (1991)'s Theory of Planned Behaviour arguing that what people intend to do is often a reliable indicator of what they actually will do (Yin & Qiu, 2021). Similar findings have been reported by Lütjens, et al. (2022) that this approach is well suited in digital markets where mapping actual behaviour is very difficult. Therefore, based on these discussions, it is believed that perceived behaviour offers a reliable alternate to actual behaviour.

The way people respond to online content also plays a role in shaping their buying intentions. Several studies show that when the content feels personalised or relevant,

people are more likely to consider buying. Chandra, et al. (2022) found that digital messages that matched users' interests led to stronger purchase intentions. Similarly, Duong, et al. (2024) found that behavioural intentions of young digital buyers is directly affected by the message clarity and tone. These findings suggest that how information is presented online plays a significant role in shaping purchase intentions. However, fewer studies have explored the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in shaping this behaviour. While AI has been greatly helpful to many online businesses in development and delivery of marketing content, consumers are becoming aware of its involvement. Chen, et al. (2024) argues that many users can often detect AI generated or enhanced content which sometimes may make them doubtful about the authenticity. This emerging concern about AI-generated disinformation has been studied very little, but is becoming more relevant as marketing automation becomes widespread (Labrecque, et al., 2025).

Similarly, few of the latest studies show that when brands are open about using AI, it can actually improve how consumers respond. If people know that AI was involved and understand how it was used to create content, they often feel more respected and better informed. Ziakis & Vlachopoulou (2023) mention that being transparent in AI-related communication helps build consumer confidence and reduces the negative feelings people might have about automation. In a similar way, Lopez & Garza (2023) found that when brands clearly explained the role of AI in creating messages, people were more likely to trust the content and even think about engaging with the brand. So overall, these findings point out that being transparent about AI can have a positive effect on how people think about buying online.

Trust is one of the key things that connects how people feel about AI-based content and what they end up doing with it. If a brand comes across as honest and the message sounds believable, people are more likely to trust it and maybe even act on what they have seen. Islam, et al. (2024) emphasise that behavioural intentions are directly influenced by the level of trust in digital content. Likewise, Mangold, et al. (2022) argue that trust acts as a psychological filter, which decides to either accept or reject the online messages. In the recent times, where e-environment is suspected to be heavily cluttered with deceptive and manipulative content, trust usually becomes the first casualty, which then affects the consumers' intentions to buy.

Based on the above discussions, this study proposes a model in which consumers' online purchase intentions is influenced by two key constructs i.e. perceived AI-generated disinformation and perceived AI transparency. These variables are expected to influence the level of trust people have in brand messages, which then shapes the way they respond. Using a deductive approach backed by the Theories of Planned Behaviour and Elaboration Likelihood Model, this study aims to explain whether AI-driven communication strategies harm or strengthen perceived purchase intentions. While many previous studies have studied AI and consumer response separately, very few have discussed the trust-based pathway, leaving a relatively new but important gap in the digital consumer behaviour (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986; (Hermann & Puntoni, 2024; Ziakis & Vlachopoulou, 2023).

Perceived AI-Generated Disinformation

Perceived AI-generated disinformation refers to the consumers' belief that the some of the online brand content they interact with is possibly generated through AI, which sometimes is manipulative, overly polished or intentionally designed to mislead them. Once this feeling of mistrust develops, it negatively influences their willingness to engage with the brand (Chen, et al., 2024).

With the advancements in technology and widespread use of artificial intelligence in marketing the line between real vs AI is increasingly becoming blur, raising further questions about the trust and authenticity (Labrecque, et al., 2025). Tools such chat-bots, content generators and deep-fakes have made it easier for marketers to develop persuasive marketing campaigns; in fact, this to some extent has automated the marketing content development. This trend however, has made it easier to fabricate or exaggerate claims, making consumers more cautious about the truthfulness of the information they receive (Ruiz, 2023). The same has been reported by Teepapal (2025) that if consumers suspect that content is AI enhanced or lacks human oversight, they may feel deceived or manipulated, which negatively affects their trust in the brand.

This issue of perceived manipulation more problematic because consumers now days are overloaded with information through different digital platforms, which too sometimes is inconsistent. Researchers such as Lopez & Garza (2023) argued that when shopping online if consumers feel that a marketing message is unauthentic, missing out on emotional appeal or clarity and is possibly made using AI algorithm or is too robotic, they tend to filter that brand out. Thus, indicating that AI-disinformation not only deals with the information being wrong but also with the content which is repetitive, emotionless or doesn't meet the consumers' expectations. This sometimes may lead them to question the overall brand reliability.

These findings can be further explained through Elaboration Likelihood Model (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986), which explains that different individuals process information differently depending upon their level of trust and resonance with the brand. So, if something doesn't seem trustworthy to them, they will be less likely to think about it more deeply and will rather focus on surface level cues or may possibly ignore it completely. This view point is also supported by Spence (1973) Signalling Theory, which states that brand messages act like signals of credibility and if these signals look like AI-generated content, consumers may view them as fake and misleading, therefore, reducing consumers' trust in those brands.

Furthermore, perceived disinformation can possibly trigger psychological resistance among consumers where they consciously reject or ignore the marketing messages which are believed to be misleading. Jamal, et al. (2023) explain that if consumers feel that a marketing content is trying hard to influence them, they may disengage altogether. When it comes to online shopping, this kind of response is very important, because most of the decisions here are dependent on the interpretations of the digital content. In short, if something feels dishonest, even an appealing product will not get attention.

Recent studies have pointed out that the impact of AI-generated disinformation is different among different age groups. For example, young consumers are more tech-savvy and can easily identify and reject the automated content. However, older users may find the same content to be neutral or sometimes useful (Chu, et al., 2022). Secondly, the platform matters a lot, for example, while content on Tiktok or Instagram may feel more natural, it may seem more artificial and less trustworthy when it comes to email or reviews (Al-Geitany, et al., 2023).

Although perceived AI- disinformation is growing research topic in Political marketing but there is still a gap in how it affects in online shopping. Therefore, this study focuses on studying how consumers see and interpret automated messages online and do they think content is misleading or too robotic.

Based on the above discussions, following hypotheses is formulated,

H₁: Perceived AI-generated disinformation negatively influences consumers' online

purchase intentions.

Perceived AI Transparency:

Perceived AI transparency refers to the openness of a brand about the use of artificial intelligence in developing its online marketing content. As discussed in the previous sections there are a number of AI tools being used nowadays, therefore, this concept reflects whether consumers feel informed about their presence and the role of AI in shaping the message they receive (Ziakis & Vlachopoulou, 2023).

While use of artificial intelligence is on the rise in a number of key online activities, such as, product recommendations, customer support, and generating advertisement content, transparency around AI usage is emerging to be a key factor in shaping consumer attitudes. Studies like Lopez & Garza (2023) reported that if consumers are informed about the use of AI, they respond positively and feel more respected and involved in the interaction. Similar findings have been reported by others that the brands, which are transparent about AI usage, are considered more trustworthy. Sahebi & Formosa (2025) stated that discomfort arising from robotic interaction could be reduced if brands are clearly communicating its users about automated content. This is more important in online shopping where consumers are exposed to overloaded marketing content across different platforms.

Furthermore, Fairness, Accountability, Transparency and Ethics (FATE) framework supports that if brands are fair about their AI usage, it creates positive brand image. For example, Jobin, et al. (2019) believe that being transparent about AI systems is not only important to be seen as ethical but also for building public trust. From online shopping perspective, this means that businesses need to be more open about their AI-usage when it's used to create online advertisements or personalization. Yang, et al. (2024) argues that perception of fairness is enhanced by transparency, which makes the consumers to better evaluate the intent behind the marketing efforts, therefore, leading to more informed and confident decision making.

Signalling theory further supports, this relationship by suggesting that AI disclosure can act as positive signals of brand's honesty and intent, creating trust in brand (Sharma & Klein, 2024). Without these signals, consumers sometimes can question the authenticity of the content or feel being manipulated, especially in online shopping where content saturation is high (Ziakis & Vlachopoulou, 2023).

The mediating role of trust is strongly shaped by how consumers perceive transparency because when people understand how AI was used in message creation, they feel more in control, and confident about the decision. Zerilli, et al. (2023) found out that if consumers have been communicated about the AI's role in recommendation systems, they are more likely to trust the message and follow with possible action. Same has been reported by Ienca (2023) that transparency can help reduce the perceived manipulation, which helps consumers feel more confident in engaging with the brands.

Although AI transparency has and is increasingly being studied by many researchers, its focus is generally more towards ethical or technological acceptance and hasn't been extensively studied to explore how it impacts consumer behaviour. Therefore, this study aims to address this gap by examining how perceived AI transparency shaped both trust and purchase intentions.

Based on the above discussions, following hypotheses has been formulated

H₂: Perceived AI transparency positively influences consumers' online purchase intentions.

Consumer Trust

Trust plays a central role in the online marketplace environment as it decides how consumers will interpret brands' messages and interact with them: either leading to purchase or ignoring the content altogether. Trust in online environment is defined as the willingness to consumers to accept brand's persuasion with the belief that the brand is reliable and acts in their best interest (Singh, et al., 2024). As the digital commerce is cluttered with artificial intelligence and algorithms, transparency and the way information is presented become the key drivers of trust information.

The element of trust becomes significantly important in online environment because physical cues are not present; therefore, it helps reduce perceived risk and uncertainty. There are many studies which highlight the importance of trust in shaping consumer purchase intentions on e-commerce platforms. For example, Wang, et al. (2022) reported that consumers' willingness to engage in online transaction is greatly increased by trust, which acts as a foundational element in the online purchase decision-making process. Their met-analytics study across different social commerce platforms have shown that trust not only increases the purchase intention but also increases satisfaction and loyalty. Similar findings have been reported by Soleimani (2021) that in online shopping consumers normally rely on online representation of the product or the brands, and trust is the one of the most crucial elements when studying consumer behaviour in this setting.

Among other things, credibility of the information and transparency are one of the key contributors to trust in online shopping. A belief supported by Veltri, et al. (2020) study, which argues that the platforms, which reduce informational ambiguity by providing clear structured information, are more likely to gain consumer trust. This is even more relevant in e-commerce where product reviews, brand claims and influencers' promotions are often blended together. Another study by Jiang & Lau (2021) suggest that if consumers perceive the information to be unbiased and verifiable, it will more likely increase their trust and likelihood of purchase.

Emotions also play a key role in how consumers will respond to online messages. For example, Beck, et al. (2023) argue that nowadays consumers are highly sensitive to fake, manipulated or over-personalized content when it comes to visiting review platforms or social shopping spaces. Their study further indicated that when platforms have a mechanism in place to flag unreliable information and clarify how messages are filtered and presented, it greatly improves users trust in the platforms. This shows that transparency and accountability are the core contributors to brand trust building. Furthermore, the nature and presentation of online content also plays a huge role. For example, Sung, et al. (2023) reported that the platforms which display a detailed balanced reviews with a clear rating system, they tend to garner higher level of trust in product quality. This explains that trust is deeply influenced by perceived fairness and integrity, which makes the consumers feel that their decisions are supported by reliable feedback and honest brand communication, therefore, increasing their purchase intention.

This discussion leads us to believe that trust acts as a mediating force between online content and consumer behaviour or intentions. While there are many other factors, which may influence online shopping behaviour, trust acts as the filter through which all other signals are processed. Singh, et al. (2024) further elaborate this by reporting that when online content is misleading or overly robotic, consumer trust reduces and if the brands openly communicate with reliability, this trust can lead to purchase and long-term consumer loyalty.

Based on the discussions above, this study conceptualizes trust as a mediator between

IVs (perceived AI-generated disinformation and AI transparency) and purchase intentions. Furthermore, following hypothesis are formulated,

H₃: Consumer trust positively influences Consumers' online purchase intentions.

H₄: Consumer trust mediates the relationship between perceived AI-generated disinformation and consumers' online purchase intentions.

H₅: Consumer trust mediates the relationship between perceived AI transparency and consumers' online purchase intentions.

Digital Literacy:

Digital literacy is defined as individual's ability to be able to access, evaluate and critically interpret the digital content, so that, they can differentiate between the exaggerated claims vs reality. Furthermore, this includes not only the technical knowledge but also cognitive and socio-emotional skills, which are necessary to stay informed and safely engage in the modern digital environment (Teepapal, 2025). In the current times when artificial intelligence is widely accepted in creating and distributing online marketing content, digital literacy is becoming significantly more important because it can influence how consumers process and react to AI-generated content, especially regarding trust formation. While many brands now continue to rely on AI, consumers with higher digital literacy are more likely to detect biases, check message's credibility and make informed decisions (Qadri, et al., 2025).

When it comes to perceived AI-generated disinformation, digital literacy may act like a psychological filter, which helps the consumers differentiate between a credible content and manipulated information. Researchers like Seker, et al., (2025) reported that consumers who are more digitally literate could better detect the algorithmic bias or deceptive AI practices, which therefore, can help in reducing the adverse effects of AI-generated disinformation on their trust in the brand messages. However, lower levels of digital literacy may leave the consumers vulnerable to persuasive but misleading content, which can hurt their brand trust in the longer run (Tiernan, et al., 2023). Therefore, it can be inferred that digital literacy moderates the relationship between AI-disinformation and consumer trust.

Similarly, digital literacy may improve the positive impact of perceived AI-transparency on consumers trust because people with higher digital literacy are better at comprehending disclosure about AI usage and could interpret transparency more positively. Their ability to detect and evaluate digital content sometimes increases the appreciation for those brands, which communicate AI involvement openly, thus developing greater trust (Mahmood, et al., 2022). Studies like Lopez and Garza (2023) reported that being transparent is not enough but it is equally important that consumers have abilities to understand the technical and ethical implications of disclosures because it will define whether they interpreted it positively or not. Therefore, digital literacy acts like an enabler, by helping consumers to value open communications, which enhances the trust-building effects of AI-transparency (Castañeda, et al., 2020).

Additionally, this moderating effect of digital literacy is also supported by Petty & Cacioppo, (1986) Elaboration likelihood model, which argues that people with higher cognitive involvement, such as, those with higher digital literacy, are more likely to engage in central processing. Furthermore, they are able to scrutinize the advertised information more deeply, weigh in arguments critically and then develop well-informed judgements about the brand message. This shows that a similar AI-generated message may have different impact on individuals and is dependent on their level of digital literacy, for example, consumers with lower digital knowledge the effects of

AI-transparency or disinformation may follow more peripheral routes rather than going for careful evaluation, therefore, leading to either misplaced trust or unjustified scepticism (Guerra-Tamez, et al., 2024).

The moderating role of digital literacy has been studied recently by many researchers in the digital marketing research. Recent studies like Aleti, et al., (2025) argued that digital competency is key factor when it comes to shaping consumers' attitudes towards technology and also in shaping their susceptibility to persuasive online content and their trust in the AI based processes. Similar findings were reported by Liu. et al., (2023) where they reported that consumers who possessed limited digital skills often felt higher levels of anxiety or confusion when they were shown an AI-driven personalized message, which as a result weakened their trust in the brand. Therefore, it is evident that digital literacy doesn't impact consumer behaviour and purchase intentions alone but also effects other variables like transparency and disinformation to create trust.

Based on these above discussions, following hypothesis have been developed,

H₆: Digital literacy moderates the negative relationship between AI-generated disinformation and consumer trust in such a way that consumers with higher literacy will have a weaker impact.

H₇: Digital literacy moderates the positive relationship between perceived AI-transparency and consumer trust in such a way that the impact is stronger for consumers with higher literacy levels.

Theoretical Framework:

Methodology and Research Design:

3.1. Research Philosophy and Approach:

This research has adopted a positivist philosophy, which is well suited for hypothesis-based study that focuses on the observable and measurable phenomenon (Saunders, et al., 2023). Furthermore, a deductive approach has been used, which is based on existing theoretical frameworks i.e. the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), Signalling Theory (Spence, 1973) and the Elaboration Likelihood Model (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986). Lastly, this research approach also helps in the testing the hypothesised relationships.

Research Design:

A quantitative, cross-sectional research design has been used to study how perceived AI-disinformation and perceived AI transparency effect the consumers' online purchase intentions where trust is taken as a mediator and digital literacy as moderator.

Data were collected at a single point in time using a structured online questionnaire, enabling efficient measurement of psychological constructs and behavioural intentions across a relatively large sample. This design is especially suitable for behavioural research involving perception-based constructs, where experimental or longitudinal designs are impractical (Grimmer & Bingham, 2013; Chen, et al., 2023).

Population and Sampling

The target population consisted of Pakistani online consumers aged 18 and above, those who have some exposure to AI-generated digital marketing content. Due to time and accessibility constraints, the study used a non-probability convenience sampling technique. This approach is frequently used in online behavioural research because of ease of access and cost-effectiveness, especially when the research aims to explore theoretical relationships rather than generalizing on larger population (Jiang & Lau, 2021).

300 responses were collected using Google Forms, which was distributed across different WhatsApp, student networks and other social media channels. This sample size meets just the minimum requirements for conducting regression-based mediation and moderation analysis using AMOS and SPSS (Hayes, 2017).

Instrument Development

Each of the variable has been measured using a 5 point Likert scale where (1 = Strongly disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree). The questions within these constructs were slightly modified for our clarity and contextual relevance of the Pakistani digital consumers. Initially, we tested the questionnaire with 30 participants to ensure its validity and comprehension. The questionnaire was adapted from the following,

No.	Construct	Questions	Adapted From
1	Demographics	1. Gender: Male / Female / Non-binary / Prefer not to say 2. Age 3. Education 4. Online Shopping Frequency 5. Monthly Spend (PKR)	-
2	Perceived AI-Generated Disinformation	1. I often question if product descriptions are exaggerated by AI. 2. It's hard to distinguish between human-written and AI-generated reviews. 3. I suspect some brands use AI to fabricate fake testimonials. 4. AI tools make it easier for sellers to spread false product claims.	(Srinivasan, 2025; Sivathanu, et al., 2023)

		5. I feel deceived when I realize marketing content was AI-generated.	
3	Perceived AI Transparency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I trust brands more when they disclose AI usage in marketing. 2. Labels like 'AI-generated' help me evaluate product information. 3. Brands explaining their AI use seem more credible. 4. I avoid brands that don't reveal their use of AI tools. 5. Transparency about AI reduces my doubts about product quality. 	(Park & Yoon, 2024; Ioku, et al., 2024)
4	Digital Literacy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I can identify signs of AI-generated content (e.g., repetitive phrases). 2. I verify product claims using external sources. 3. I understand how AI tools like ChatGPT are used in marketing. 4. I'm confident spotting fake reviews or manipulated info. 5. I cross-check multiple sources before trusting brand messages. 	(Mahmood, et al., 2022; Seker, et al., 2025)
5	Consumer Trust	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I believe brands provide accurate product information. 2. I rely on brand descriptions when making purchases. 3. Brands I follow rarely mislead customers intentionally. 4. Transparent communication increases my brand loyalty. 5. I trust brands with clear AI policies more. 	(Guerra-Tamez, et al., 2024; Park & Yoon, 2024)
6	Online consumers' Purchase Intentions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I intend to buy from brands transparent about AI usage. 2. I'm willing to pay more for brands that disclose AI-generated content. 3. I actively seek brands honest about AI in marketing. 4. I avoid brands that hide their use of AI tools. 5. I plan to buy more from brands with clear AI policies. 	(Korzaan, 2003; Song, et al., 2024)

Data Analysis:

To present a comprehensive analysis measurements and structural model was estimated through SEM modelling using AMOS, because SEM analysis serves as one of the most appropriate method to study complex multiple predictor models simultaneously. A detailed report is presented in this section as follow,

Reliability Assessment:

For reliability assessment, Cronbach’s alpha was used to check the internal consistency of each element within each scale. All four variables showed a strong reliability where the values of alpha exceeded the minimum acceptance threshold of 0.70 as shown in the table below,

Construct	Cronbach’s Alpha
Perceived AI Disinformation	0.818
Perceived AI Transparency	0.834
Consumer Trust	0.828
Digital Literacy	0.834

Table 1: Reliability test

All values present in the table are within the range of 0.81-0.834 meaning that every item is reliability measuring our intended constructs. Furthermore, this also indicates that the responses were highly correlated within each variable, indicating that a consistent and stable perception was shown by among all participants.

Measurement Model Evaluation (CFA):

To assess the validity of all the latent variables, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed, where the results showed that all standardized factor loadings for Perceived AI disinformation, perceived AI transparency, consumer trust and consumer purchase intentions are well above 0.80, with many going beyond 0.90. Such strong loadings show that all our observed items are closely representing their respective latent variables and significantly contribute to explaining construct variance. The following table shows the same,

Construct	Item	Loading	Interpretation
Perceived Disinformation	AI Disinfo1	.926	Strong indicator
	AI Disinfo2	.980	High reliability
	AI Disinfo3	1.015	Strong item
	AI Disinfo4	.949	Excellent
	AI Disinfo5	1.000	Reference
Perceived Transparency	AI Trans1	1.000	Reference
	AI Trans2	.896	Very strong
	AI Trans3	1.020	Excellent
	AI Trans4	1.028	Excellent
	AI Trans5	.924	Strong
Consumer Trust	Trust1	1.000	Reference
	Trust2	1.037	Excellent
	Trust3	.943	High loading
	Trust4	1.007	Strong
	Trust5	1.133	Very strong
Consumer purchase intention	Online PI1	1.025	Strong
	Online PI2	1.070	Strong
	Online PI3	1.084	Excellent
	Online PI4	1.076	Excellent
	Online PI5	1.000	Reference

Table 2: CFA analysis

Structural Equation Model (SEM) Fit:

A combination of absolute, incremental and parsimony-based indices to assess the overall model fit, which collectively showed an excellent fit between the hypothesised model and the collected data. For instance, chi-square to degrees of freedom ratio ($\chi^2/df = 1.540$) is well below the recommended level of 3.0 which indicates that the covariance structure assumed by the model sufficiently matches the sample data.

Furthermore, incremental fit and absolute fit indices also surpasses their respective benchmarks as shown below,

Fit Index	Threshold	Obtained Value	Assessment
χ^2/df	< 3	1.540	Excellent
GFI	> .85	.908	Good
AGFI	> .80	.887	Good
CFI	> .95	.956	Excellent
IFI	> .95	.956	Excellent
TLI	> .90	.950	Excellent
RMSEA	< .06	.043	Excellent
RMSEA CI	—	.033–.052	Narrow & stable
PCLOSE	> .05	.912	Close fit supported
Hoelter .05	> 200	227	Adequate sample

Table 3: SEM Model fit

By looking at these, we can decisively say that the combined fit indices justifies with going forward with the interpretations of the SEM model.

Structural Model Results:

We used SEM analysis to evaluate the relationships among our variables i.e. Perceived AI Disinformation (Disinfo), Perceived AI Transparency (Trans), Consumer trust (Trust), Digital Literacy (D.Lit) and Purchase Intentions (P.Intent). The results, standardized regression weights and statistics are shown as below in the table, (***) p-value < 0.001)

Path	β	S.E.	C.R.	p-value	Interpretation
Disinfo → Trust	-0.567	.063	-8.985	***	Significant negative effect
Trans → Trust	0.592	.063	9.381	***	Significant positive effect
Disinfo → P.Intent	-0.195	.075	-2.585	.010	Significant negative effect
Trans → P.Intent	0.076	.075	1.007	.314	Not significant
Trust → P.Intent	0.758	.134	5.672	***	Strong significant effect

Table 4: SEM Model Results

Effect of Perceived AI Disinformation on Consumer Trust:

It was observed that a negative and significant ($\beta = -0.567$) effect of Perceived AI Disinformation exists on Consumer Trust, meaning that when an online content is perceived by the consumers as generated by AI, their trust fades away in the brand communications. Furthermore, a strong and stable relationship is supported by the extremely high critical ration (CR = -8.985). In summary, higher levels of concerns about AI-driven misinformation results into damaging consumer confidence and credibility in the brand message.

Effect of Perceived AI Transparency on Consumer Trust:

A strong positive effect of transparency has been shown on consumer Trust ($\beta = 0.592, p < .001$), which means that when companies are open about their AI usage and explain how it was utilized, it can restore and build the trust in the brand messages. If we look at the negative effect of disinformation and the strong positive effect of being transparent, it becomes apparent that these two forces are competing to influence trust.

Direct effect on Consumers' Online Purchase Intentions:

By looking at the results we can see that there is a significant negative effect of Disinformation on the purchase intention ($\beta = -0.195, p = .010$), showing that misleading or AI-generated content reduces consumers' intent to purchase. Whereas, when we look at the Transparency's effect on the purchase intention, that is insignificant ($\beta = 0.076, p = .314$), which means that Transparency stand-alone cannot impact the consumers' intent to purchase online unless it is mediated through trust.

Effect of Consumer Trust on Online Purchase Intentions:

A very strong effect of Consumer trust has been observed on the purchase intentions, significantly predicting the consumers' intent to purchase ($\beta = 0.758$). This means that consumers' trust is one of the most important factors when it comes to purchasing online because they will buy from those brands, only the ones they trust.

Moderation Analysis through Digital Literacy:

By using the latent interaction terms in SEM, moderation was tested which is an advanced and accurate method of checking moderation while accounting for the measurement errors. The results are shown in the table below,

Interaction Path	β	S.E.	C.R.	p-value	Interpretation
Disinfo-DL→Trust	0.235	.039	5.969	***	D.Lit weakens the negative effect
Trans-DL → Trust	0.253	.042	6.086	***	D.Lit strengthens the positive effect

Table 5: Moderating role of Digital Literacy (DL)

There was a significant and positive interaction observed between the Perceived AI Disinformation and Digital Literacy, showing that consumers who have high digital literacy are less affected the AI disinformation. This is because they're able to evaluate the online information more effectively and can identify biases, manipulative content much easily which doesn't sharply decrease their trust levels by exposure to disinformation.

A significantly positive interaction between the Perceived AI transparency and Digital Literacy was recorded, meaning that the consumers who have higher level of digital literacy welcome the brands, which are transparent about their AI-usage, and this enhances their trust as well.

By combining both, we can say that Digital literacy has both a protective and also a trust amplifying factor.

Mediation Analysis:

The findings of the mediation analysis are reported in the table below,

Relationship	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect via Trust	Mediation Type
Disinfo → P.Intent	Significant	Significant	Partial Mediation
Trans → P.Intent	Not significant	Significant	Full Mediation

Table 6: Mediation effect

Perceived AI Disinformation effects the Consumers' online purchase intentions in two ways, stated as below,

Directly through negatively significant path

Indirectly through Consumer Trust

This two-way influence shows that, a partial mediation exists, meaning that Disinformation negatively effects the purchase intention independently as well as through negatively effecting the trust.

As discussed previously, there wasn't a direct significant effect of Perceived AI Transparency on Purchase intention, however, through a mediated path i.e. through consumer trust the effect is significant indicating a full mediation where transparency positively influences the trust which then leads the consumer to purchase products/services online.

Discussion

This study looked at how Perceived AI disinformation and AI Transparency effect the consumers' online purchase intentions with consumer trust as mediator and digital literacy as the moderator. Our findings have shown some key insights that contribute to the theoretical knowledge as well as some understanding of the consumer behaviour while shopping online.

Firstly, we have seen a negative effect of Disinformation on Consumer trust ($\beta = -0.567$) which confirms that when consumers are exposed to misleading or AI-generated content, their trust in that brand goes away and they stop trusting its messages, aligning with the past research (Singh, et al., 2024; Wang, et al., 2022). Furthermore, a significant negative effect of disinformation on the consumers' purchase intentions ($\beta = -0.195$) shows that it not only will erode trust but stand-alone can stop the customers from purchasing and trust partially is mediating this relationship, showing its importance where it can act as a buffer between the disinformation and the purchase intention.

Secondly, it was observed that Perceived AI Transparency has a positive impact on the Consumers Trust ($\beta = 0.592$), showing that when the organizations are transparent about their use of AI in generating marketing messages, that can help restore and build trust in consumers. As discussed before, although, Transparency doesn't have a direct significant impact on the consumers' purchase intentions, full mediation shows that transparency creates and enhances trust which then can lead the consumers to purchase online. A belief, which was reported by researchers before as well, for example, Yang, et al. (2024) believed that transparency can elevate the consumers' trust levels significantly which then leads them to make a purchase or hold a positive perception of the brand.

Thirdly, through moderation analysis we were able to observe that digital literacy can greatly impact the disinformation and transparency's effect on consumers' trust. As discussed before, higher levels of digital literacy meant that consumers are able to identify misleading or AI-generated messages effectively, which reduces the negative effects of disinformation on trust. Furthermore, if the brands are open about their AI-usage, consumers feel like the brand has been honest to them which can increase their trust in the brand message, which subsequently leads them to purchase.

Lastly, it has been observed that Consumer Trust stand-alone is a strong predictor of the consumer purchase intention ($\beta = 0.758$), further solidifying the idea that the trust plays a crucial role in driving the consumers to purchase in the modern AI-driven marketing environment. This provides the marketers deep insights to develop their

strategies in such a way, which will enhance consumers' trust in the modern e-commerce.

Implications:

This study provides several contributions to both;

The existing literature on AI-driven marketing, online consumer behaviour and purchase intentions

Practical implication includes a detailed overview of the online marketplace, how consumers behave online where they're primarily influenced by trust and transparency. Furthermore, with the modern AI technology the consumers are also evolving and becoming more aware of the AI-generated content, which can lead them to either trust or distrust a brand depending upon how it was used.

Limitations

There are a few limitations to this study as discussed below,

Data was collected at a single point and from only roughly 300 respondents, which makes the study non-generalizable for the larger population. Therefore, longitudinal data collection with a larger sample size is needed.

We used purchase intention to measure the online consumer behaviour, which can give some close indication but still actual consumer behaviour study is required.

Limited scope of AI factors has been discussed in this study as we stayed focused on Disinformation, Transparency, literacy factors, whereas there can be other factors too which can impact the intention, for example, personalization, algorithm's accuracy and privacy concerns. These can be studied in the future to present a complete picture.

Conclusion

This study has shown that Perceived AI-Disinformation can greatly impact the consumers' trust which can then lead them away from purchasing, however, when it comes to being transparent about the use of AI in creating marketing messages, it can increase consumers' trust which can lead them to making a purchase online. Additionally, Digital literacy also plays a pivotal role in either protecting or elevating trust as consumers with higher literacy can easily identify the AI-generated content, which can sometime act as a buffer between erosion of trust, and when the brand was being transparent, it increases trust greatly, ultimately leading to a sale.

In conclusion, these findings shed a light on the importance of the being transparent in online marketing in the modern times when consumers can identify and distinguish between human generated or AI-generated content with great accuracy. All brands want their customers to trust them and that trust in the online marketplace is much dependant on being transparent.

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